

FEATURES OF BASKETBALL CLASSES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: The article describes the features of basketball as a means of physical culture, the specifics of basketball training in higher education institutions. Characterized content content and basic skills and rules for conducting basketball lessons.

Key words: basketball, technical and tactical training, physical training, students, higher education, health.

Introduction. At the present stage of development of society, adolescents and young men acquire special value [2, 3]. In the system of training university students, physical education is an important means of developing a healthy lifestyle, developing and restoring physical and spiritual strength, rehabilitation and health correction.

The State National Program sets the task of ensuring in every educational institution the conditions for training and education of a morally, physically and mentally healthy person accepted in the world [1, 4, 5].

In modern life, the increasing use of physical exercise is aimed not at achieving high results, but at increasing their health-improving effects on the general public [6, 8, 9]. To solve such a global problem, the most effective means are, first of all, sports games. One of the most popular sports games among young people in the modern world is basketball, which is becoming increasingly popular in the Republic of Uzbekistan as a sports game every year.

Basketball is an athletic game characterized by high motor activity and significant tension in game actions and, moreover, is at the stage of rapid creative growth, characterized by tendencies to intensify various actions in attack and defense [7, 10, 11]. The variety of these actions and the gaming activity itself have unique properties for the formation of vital skills and abilities, the comprehensive development of the physical and psychological qualities of students. Basketball is one of the most popular games among university students [12, 13].

The reasons for this popularity, according to many authors, are diverse; a number of authors believe that this fact is due to the high educational and health value of the game [14, 16].

Mastering the basics of modern basketball requires mastering the basics of its technique and tactics. Techniques are divided into those performed in defense and attack, the technique of playing in attack includes movement technique - the position of the players (stance), running, walking, jumping, stopping, turning, and ball possession technique - catching, passing, dribbling, throwing, which plays a special role important role in the game [15]. Technique in defense includes movement technique and technique of mastering the ball and countering the opponent - covering, knocking out, rebounding, mastering the rebound. Attack and defense tactics include individual, group and team actions. Each of these groups is divided into different types and includes different methods of gaming activity [17, 18].

An important thing in basketball is the distribution of team players according to playing roles, for which there are certain requirements. The center should preferably be tall, athletic, and have excellent endurance and jumping ability. The attacker is characterized by tall height, speed, jumping ability, a developed sense of time and space, sniper abilities, skill in the game situation, and boldly and decisively carrying out an attack. The defender must be as fast, agile and resilient as possible, sensible and attentive. Players of each role must be able to perform other functions, respond in a timely and adequate manner to all actions of partners and players of the

opposing team, and constantly monitor their location and the location of the ball [19, 20].

The general goal of conducting basketball classes with students in universities is the comprehensive physical development of boys and girls, strengthening their health, acquiring a certain level of technical and tactical skill in basketball, and preparing for socially useful activities in future life. Students' readiness for basketball lessons is determined by the presence of certain motor skills, theoretical knowledge of the basics of basketball, personal motivation, and individual psychological qualities.

The content of educational and game basketball lessons differs, depending on the physical and technical preparedness of the student. The selection of exercises for technical and tactical training should be carried out according to the principle from simple to complex. In general, the basis of technical initial training is: learning the simplest techniques of catching and dribbling the ball, playing a pass, aiming before throwing. The content of technical and tactical training has a sequence: interacting with the ball with an opponent one-on-one (without contact actions), choosing and igniting free spaces on the court by players without the ball, training shots into the basket, knocking the ball out while the opponent is dribbling and covering shots, dribbling the ball with opposition from the opponent, opening on the court in motion after returning the pass, shooting with opposition, fast breaks with a throw into the basket, choosing a place while picking up the ball that bounced off the backboard, collective attacks using centers. players, screens.

To improve technical and tactical actions, the content of the training session should be structured in the following sequence: shots into the basket from different distances, the use of attack techniques and feints in conditions of tight guarding, various methods of passing the ball while moving and jumping, blocking shots, organizing a positional attack by centers, hidden passes and discounts, finishing the ball into the basket while jumping, dribbling and passing and shooting in difficult conditions.

The system of physical training exercises consists of two main sections - general and special. The selection of exercises for general training includes exercises from such sports that will contribute to the overall physical development of players. Such exercises are usually included in the physical training system of athletes in sports such as gymnastics, athletics, and swimming. This complex also includes various sports games. When drawing up lesson plans, you must comply with a number of requirements:

- taking into account tasks and working conditions;
- concreteness and possibility, variability;
- acceptability and prospects.

Management of basketball classes - clearly defines which exercises, in what volume, sequence, ratio, with what intensity should be used in each period or stage of classes, taking into account the patterns of development of physical training of students of higher educational institutions in order to obtain results in the required time frame.

To achieve results in basketball among university students, it is necessary to conduct not only games in team or doubles conditions, but also to conduct in parallel a whole range of physical training classes (gymnastics, athletics and swimming). In particular, gymnastic exercises:

1. Exercises without objects to strengthen the muscles of the torso of basketball players, upper and lower extremities.
2. Stretching exercises with maximum amplitude, various swings and jerks with arms, bends that should be performed with maximum amplitude, lunges, splits and a number of other exercises aimed at developing the flexibility and plasticity of players.
3. Exercises to develop coordination and accuracy of movement.
4. Resistance exercises.
5. Exercises with objects (dumbbells, balls, jump ropes, met balls).
6. Exercises on the gymnastic wall, parallel bars, bench.

7. Jumping over the bar in a straight run-up, vault.

Athletics exercises:

1. Running at short and medium distances.
2. Running alternating with walking.
3. Running up the stairs, on the sand.
4. Jumping up, pushing off with one or two legs.
5. Long and high jumps.
6. Half squat jumps.
7. Athletics relay races.
8. Discus throw, shot throw, javelin throw with left and right hand.

Swimming exercises:

1. Swimming at a distance of 25, 50 and 100 m in different styles.
2. Performing a turn after pushing off from the wall of the pool.

Conclusions. Thus, general conditioning in basketball uses many different physical exercises. However, in addition to the rational selection of funds, the correct determination of the scale of physical activity and the distribution of exercises during educational and training sessions is important.

Consequently, playing basketball involves high physical activity of players; in the process of physical education of students of a higher educational institution, basketball satisfies the needs for physical activity. A variety of movements characteristic of basketball, such as walking, running, stopping, turning, jumping, catching, throwing and dribbling the ball, help strengthen the nervous system, musculoskeletal system, improve metabolism and the activity of all body systems of students.

References:

1. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2022). Физическая активность как один из факторов здорового образа жизни и воспитания молодежи. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(7), 283-292.

2. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2020). Анализ разбора стиля игры команды для контратаки в футболе. *Вестник науки и образования*, (7-2 (85)), 60-62.
3. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2020). Роль планирования тренировочного процесса и мотивации на успешный результат чемпионата. *Достижения науки и образования*, (9 (63)), 50-53.
4. Бердиева, Х. К. (2018). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (3), 23-25.
5. Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Теоретические основы развития ловкости у детей 6-7 лет посредством подвижных игр и игровых упражнений с мячом. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 43-47.
6. Бердиева, Х. К. (2022). Ҳаракатли ўйинлар-болалар жисмоний фаоллигини оширишининг муҳим воситаларидан биридир. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1 (97)), 433-437.
7. Даниева, Я. Ч., Салимов, У. Ш., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2015). Спортивные мероприятия – воспитывающий фактор человека нового общества. *Университетский спорт: здоровье и процветание нации.* –2015.
8. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (2), 111-113.
9. Хакназаров, К. К. (2020). Факторы, определяющие физическое воздействие в игре баскетбол. *Достижения науки и образования*, (10 (64)), 53-55.
10. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Основы формирования культуры движений младших школьников. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 225-228.
11. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Физиологические особенности, влияющие на развитие силовых способностей учащихся старших классов. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 326-329.

12. Омонтурдиев, О. К. (2020). Значение физической культуры и спорта в создании крепкой семьи. *Достижения науки и образования*, (9 (63)), 53-55.
13. Умбаров, Д. М., & Хакназаров, К. К. (2020). Условия формирования профессиональной культуры у будущих учителей физического образования. *Вестник науки и образования*, (8-1 (86)), 82-84.
14. Усманходжаев, Т. С., Бердиева, Х. К., & Тошпулатова, А. Т. (2021). Двигательная активность и народные игры-эффективные средства, методы и формы организации физического совершенствования подрастающего поколения. *Евразийский союз ученых*, (1-1 (82)), 51-53.
15. Усманходжаев, Т. С., ДУ, У. Д. С., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2020). Роль подвижных игр в повышение двигательной активности детей. *Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги*, 647.
16. Шаймарданов, Р. Н. (2019). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (6-1), 166-169.
17. Karimovna, B. X. Methods of application and use of mobile games in the process of complex training of young handball players at the initial stage. *Creation of ethnographies with popular traditions*, 11(13), 14.
18. Karimova, B. X. The Effectiveness of the Use of Movement Games in the Early Training Phase of Young Handball Players. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(9), 172-175.
19. Karimovna, B. K., & Kushayevich, K. K. (2019). Development of physical culture and sports as the main factor social development of the young generation. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(12).
20. Kurbanovich, A. B. (2022). Increasing physical culture and sports skills. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 77-78.